

The role of ancient Iraqi People (Sumerian, Assyrian, Babylonian and Arabian) in the development of medicine as viewed by western writers

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Abstract

The name Mesopotamia (meaning "the land between the rivers") refers to the geographic region which lies near the Tigris and Euphrates Rivers [In Iraq] and not to any particular civilization. Over the course of several millennia, many civilizations developed, collapsed, and were replaced in this fertile region. However, the first civilization developed in Mesopotamia. The origins of civilization can be traced to a group of people living in southern Mesopotamia called the Sumerians.

The aim of this paper is to review the views of the distinguished western writers regarding the role of ancient people of Iraq in the development of Medicine.

Key words: Development of Medicine, Iraqi people

Introduction: The first human civilization

The name Mesopotamia (meaning "the land between the rivers") refers to the geographic region which lies near the Tigris and Euphrates Rivers [In Iraq] and not to any particular civilization. In fact,

over the course of several millennia, many civilizations developed, collapsed, and were replaced in this fertile region. However, the first civilization developed in Mesopotamia. The origins of civilization can be traced to a group of people living in southern Mesopotamia called the Sumerians. By c.3500 BCE, the Sumerians had developed many of the features that characterized subsequent civilizations. Towns grew to be cities, an early form of pictographic writing was used, metal working had begun, and temples were built on a monumental scale. Generally speaking, however, true civilization is said to have begun around 3100 BCE with the development of cuneiform writing. Cuneiform was a system of writing established by the Sumerians which required the use of a stylus in order to make wedge-shaped marks on wet clay tablets, once the tablets were dry they could be stored, transported, etc. After its development, cuneiform became the dominant system of writing in Mesopotamia for over 2000 years. Even after Sumerian became extinct as a spoken language, many other Near Eastern cultures continued to write using cuneiform.

As a result of its extensive use of several centuries, many cuneiform tablets have survived. These tablets provide historians with the opportunity to glimpse the culture of the ancient Mesopotamian civilizations [1, 2].

Mesopotamian Medicine: Available evidence

Most of the information available to modern scholars comes from cuneiform tablets [1, 2]. Many of the tablets that do mention medical practices have survived from the library of Assurbanipal, the last great king of Assyria. The library of Assurbanipal was housed in the king's palace at Nineveh, and when the palace was burned by invaders, around 20,000 clay tablets were baked (and thereby preserved) by the great fire. In the early 1920's, the 660 medical tablets from the library of Assurbanipal were published by Campbell Thompson. Other medical texts have been published more recently. For example, Franz Kocher has published a series of volumes called *Die Babylonisch-Assyrische Medizin*. The first four of these contain 420 tablets found from sites other than Assurbanipal's library, including the library of a medical practitioner (an asipu) from Neo-Assyrian Assur, as well as Middle Assyrian and Middle Babylonian texts. The remaining two volumes of Kocher's work augment Campbell Thompson, providing new joins of broken fragments and much material uncovered in the British Museum. At least one more volume of Nineveh texts has been announced. In addition, the series *Spaet Babylonische Texte aus Uruk* contains some 30 medical texts not included in Kocher's work [3, 4, 5].

Western writers Views

Samuel Noah Kramer

Samuel Noah Kramer considered the Sumerian pharmacological tablets as the first pharmacopoeia [6]. This earliest pharmacopoeia is present in the University of Pennsylvania museum. The Sumerian and Assyro-Babylonian pharmacological tablets give names for drugs and medicinal materials in parallel columns [7].

John L. Webb

John L. Webb in 1957 [3] Head, Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, University of Southern California, Los Angeles, Calif.] wrote when describing the discovery of the earliest medical document by Samuel Noah Kramer in Iraq "The medical profession can justly be proud that their earliest document is from this people and embodies within it the sincere attempt to treat disease rationally"[3]

Morris Jastrow

Morris Jastrow [Professor of Semitic Languages in the University of Pennsylvania] in 1913 wrote "While we should be careful not to exaggerate the achievements of ancient civilizations, it is, notwithstanding, surprising to find that the Babylonian and Assyrian healers" advanced as far as they did in the recognition of so large a number of specific disease's in supplying these diseases with names, and in defining in many cases varieties of the same disease" [4] Jastrow view is supported by

scientific paper entitled “Diseases of Babylon: an examination of selected texts” [8].

Stubb and Bleight

In summarizing the effects of Arabian in the development of medicine **Stubb and Bleight** stated in 1931 “With Arabs began the real craft of apothecaries” [9]

Max Meyerhof

Meyerhof in 1944 wrote in his book “Pharmacology during the golden age of Arabian Medicine” “The establishment of hospitals was originated by Arabians” [10]

Max Meyerhof brought the attention to the gynecological and obstetrical instruments used by the Arabian doctors. He stated “In any event the speculum, the forceps, the lever and the crotchet, mark in a special way the original Arab genius. It is also shown that the Arabs had developed a clear practical idea of what was normal, of what varieties of abnormality were to be met with and, by no means least, of prognosis, in obstetrical practice [11].

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